

ORIGINAL RESEARCH article

Knowledge and attitudes towards stroke in semi-urban communities in North Central Nigeria

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Abstract: Stroke and its associated disabilities are a growing public health challenge in many developing countries where a combination of poor awareness and poor medical care is driving up mortality rates. The rising cases are attributed to the rising prevalence of uncontrolled hypertension, obesity, smoking, alcohol abuse, and diabetes mellitus within the population. The prevention of stroke through awareness, knowledge, and lifestyle modification is a common approach used in public health intervention programs. Awareness and knowledge of stroke vary widely between communities partly because of access to relevant health information. This study assessed awareness, knowledge of stroke risk factors, and attitude toward stroke prevention. This study was a community-based survey among adults ≥ 40 years old in semi-urban communities of two local government area councils of Benue State, North Central Nigeria. The sixteen-item questionnaire used in this study is subdivided into socio-demographic information, knowledge of risk factors, symptoms of stroke, current morbidity, and attitude toward stroke prevention. The survey was done using two adults per household selected using simple random method and completed questionnaires were retrieved for analysis. The Chi-square test was used to determine the association between demographic variables and knowledge of stroke. The result showed poor levels of stroke awareness (47.3%), knowledge (44.6%), symptoms (44.6%), risk factors (20.6%), and symptoms (44.6%). Awareness of stroke and its risk factors is significantly association with age, gender, marital status, educational status, occupation, and income. Many respondents had poor knowledge of stroke and its risk factors. There is a need for improvement in stroke awareness in underserved communities, particularly those with limited access to mass media.

Introduction

Stroke is a disease of multiple etiologies affecting all ages and genders, although older adults > 65 years have a higher risk [1, 2]. The disease accounts for 3.1% of the global disease burden and is directly responsible for 10.8% of all mortality among adults [3-5]. Recent projections indicate that stroke will rise to 23 million new cases annually resulting in 7.8 million deaths by the year 2030 [6, 7]. Several studies have reported a rising incidence of stroke among younger age groups [8, 9] as well as premature deaths [10]. It is estimated that up to 85.0% of strokes resulting in premature deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries [9, 11], although some studies have reported slightly lower mortality rates [12]. While the incidence of stroke is reportedly on the decline in high-income countries, there is a rising number of cases in low- and middle-income countries [13]. Recent epidemiological studies estimated that 15.0% of hospital admissions in sub-Saharan Africa are

related to either stroke or its complications [14]. Several studies suggested that the prevalence of stroke in sub-Saharan Africa is largely underreported as many cases are not also presented to hospitals, particularly from rural areas [15-17]. In Nigeria, stroke prevalence from health facilities and community-based studies estimated prevalence to be around 21.0%-45.0% and reported a mortality rate of 30.0-50.0% [18, 19]. The rising incidence of stroke in low- and middle-income countries is partly driven by increasing risk factors such as the high burden of hypertension, aging population, obesity, and other risk factors [11, 20, 21]. Population-based studies reported that 30.0%-40.0% of strokes are directly linked to uncontrolled hypertension, smoking, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus, obesity, alcoholism, and a sedentary lifestyle [22]. Interestingly, these risk factors are largely responsible for cardiovascular diseases and chronic heart failure [23, 24]. There is evidence to indicate that population awareness, access to preventive care, and reduction in risk factors significantly reduce the incidence of stroke among high-risk groups [25-27]. While the reduction in stroke risk through modification of risky life factors is well known, lack of awareness, poor knowledge, early warning signs, and poor treatment-seeking behavior present significant challenges to prevention, treatment, and long-term prognosis [28, 29]. Several studies from sub-Saharan African countries reported poor awareness and knowledge of risk factors [30-33], although satisfactory knowledge has also been reported [34, 35]. While contrasting levels of knowledge have been reported in several Nigerian studies [36-38], most of the results have been poor [39]. Stroke-related disability is associated with a severe impact on quality of life, psychological distress, and socio-economic well-being [29, 40, 41]. Therefore, stroke prevention is a public health need for which success depends on individual and community action. Awareness and knowledge of risk factors are critical for individuals taking responsibility for prevention, screening for risk factors, and adopting healthier lifestyles. This study, therefore, aims to assess awareness, knowledge of risk factors, and attitudes toward stroke in a semi-urban community.

Materials and methods

Study setting: The study was carried out in Oju and Obi local government areas which are located in the South-Central part of Benue State. They share a common boundary with four local government areas which include Gwer East (North), Konshisha (East), Otukpo (West), and Ado (South) on Latitude 6° 52' 12.00"N and Longitude 8° 25' 12.00"E). The area has two public general hospitals located at local government headquarters and several primary healthcare centers spread around rural/semi-rural communities. The survey was carried out in selected five semi-urban communities in each local council area within a 10 km radius of the administrative headquarters.

Study design: This was a community-based survey of residents using a multistage sampling method. In the first stage, five communities consisting of several villages were selected based on the availability of a primary healthcare facility and social amenities. This is followed by a selection of one village in each of the selected communities. In the final stage, three major streets were selected for household survey. The survey was done using a maximum of two adults per household with a total of 100 respondents in each survey area.

Sample size: The sample size was calculated using the formula below and based on a stroke prevalence estimate of 25.0% in Nigeria [39]. The formula: $n = Z^2 PQ/e^2 \times deff.$, Where n sample size, $Z=1.96$ at 95% confidence interval, $P =$ prevalence of stroke (25%), $Q = 1 - P$, $e =$ margin of error (5.0%), $deff =$ design effect of 1.2 to adjust for clustering effect. An attrition rate of 20.0% was factored in to give a sample size of 415 respondents, however, a total of 600 respondents were surveyed from each local council area.

Questionnaire/administration: The questionnaire used in the survey was adopted from previous studies [34, 42, 43]. It consists of seven sections relating to knowledge of risk factors (12 items), the primary source of stroke information (4 items), perception of stroke (6 items), awareness (5 items), knowledge of symptoms (9

items), personal lifestyle risk factors (4 items) and personal risk assessment (one item). While all items were rated on a three-point Likert scale, personal risk assessment is on a four-point scale (likely, average, marginal, and unlikely). A cumulative score of $\geq 70.0\%$ correct responses in each domain was considered satisfactory. The selected households were visited by a pair of trained local healthcare workers and a questionnaire was self-administered on one or two respondents per household (≥ 40 years old) after obtaining verbal consent. The respondents with non-formal education were assisted by data collectors who speak the local language. A total of 1200 questionnaires were administered out of which 1000 were usable giving an 83.3% return rate.

Ethical approval: The approval of this study was obtained from the health research ethics committee of Benue State Ministry of Health, Makurdi (MoH/STA/204/VOL.1/119).

Statistical analysis: The data was entered into Microsoft Excel, SPSS version 21 for descriptive and inferential statistics, and was summarized using descriptive statistics for knowledge of risk factors, symptoms, awareness, and perception, while the Chi-square test was used to determine the association between demographic variables, knowledge of stroke, and its risk factors. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic data showed that 52.2% of the respondents are males and 55.8% are married. The mean age of respondents was 44.6 ± 14.1 years and 77.8% have primary level education and above (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Demographic data of the respondents

Variable	Frequency (%)
Gender	
Male	522 (52.2%)
Female	478 (47.8%)
Marital status	
Single	98 (09.8)
Married	558 (55.8)
Divorced	194 (19.4)
Widowed	150 (15.0)
Education	
Nonformal	222 (22.2)
Primary	188 (18.8)
Secondary	400 (40.0)
Tertiary	190 (19.0)
Occupation	
Family	222 (22.2)
Business	208 (20.8)
Civil servant	190 (19.0)
Housewife	380 (38.0)
Age (year)	
≤ 40	198 (19.8)
41-50	226 (22.6)
51-60	258 (25.8)
61-70	188 (18.8)
≥ 71	130 (13.0)
Mean age (SD)	50.7 ± 17.8
Income/month (\$)	
≤ 40	290 (29.0)
41-80	388 (38.8)
81-120	258 (25.8)
121-160	48 (4.8)
161-200	16 (1.6)
Mean income	64.8 ± 38.1

N1200 to IUSD was used for calculations

In **Figure 1**, the most self-reported chronic diseases with stroke risk included hypertension (55.3%) and diabetes mellitus (23.0%).

Figure 1: Self-reported chronic diseases with a high risk of stroke

In **Figure 2**, 47.0% of the respondents correctly identified previous stroke as a major stroke risk and poorer score for knowledge of alcohol (34.5%), cigarette smoking (36.8%), and sedentary lifestyle (21.4%) as other risk factors.

Figure 2: Knowledge of risk factors reported by the respondents

Figure 4 shows that the major sources of stroke information were community health workers (50.6%), radio/television (24.3%), family/friends (14.0%), and print media (10.7%).

Figure 3: Sources of stroke information

In **Figure 4**, stroke perception among the respondents was poor as 39.4% recognized unhealthy lifestyles as a risk factor and therefore preventable (31.8%). However, 90.0% of the respondents believe that stroke is inherited or transmissible and 24.8% understand that the effect of stroke is not reversible on treatment.

Figure 4: Perception of stroke among the respondents

In **Figure 5**, 51.7% of the respondents have never heard about stroke, and those who heard from community health workers (26.8%), family/friends (08.2%), and mass media (07.6%) among others. 02.3% became aware because they witnessed somebody with a stroke (03.4%) or a family member/friend living with a stroke.

Figure 5: Awareness of stroke among the respondents

Among those who have heard or have some knowledge of stroke difficulty in walking (78.9%), speech difficulties (69.4%), loss of sensation (63.7%), and paralysis (37.1%) were the commonly identified symptoms (**Figure 6**). Among respondents with awareness of stroke, 44.5% believed that they are unlikely to suffer from stroke while a third considered themselves to have average risk (31.2%) and marginal risk (05.1%). 19.2% of the respondents agree that there is a likelihood of stroke based on their current lifestyle (**Figure 7**).

Figure 6: Knowledge of stroke symptoms among the respondents

Figure 7: Perceived risk of stroke

In **Table 2**, there was a significant association between knowledge of stroke and demographic factors including gender, marital status, educational status, occupation, age, and income level ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Association between demographic variables and knowledge of stroke

	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Chi-square	P value
Gender				
Male	166 (16.6)	356 (35.6)	12.54	0.004
Female	226 (22.6)	252 (25.2)		
Marital Status				
Single	68 (06.8)	30 (3.0)	15.3	0.002
Married	228 (22.8)	330 (33.0)		
Divorced	78 (07.8)	116 (11.6)		
Widowed	58 (5.8)	92 (9.2)		
Educational status				
Non formal	48 (04.8)	174 (17.4)	66.98	<0.001
Primary	64 (06.4)	104 (10.4)		
Secondary	82 (16.4)	236 (23.6)		
Tertiary	136 (13.6)	54 (5.4)		
Occupation				
Business	88 (8.8)	120 (12.0)	62.12	<0.001
Farming	24 (02.4)	198 (19.8)		
Civil servant	120 (12.0)	70 (7.0)		
Housewife	172 (17.2)	208 (20.8)		
Age (yrs.)				
≤40	54 (05.4)	144 (14.4)	38.06	<0.001
41-50	128 (12.8)	98 (9.8)		
51-60	172 (17.2)	86 (8.6)		
61-70	108 (10.8)	80 (8.0)		
≥71	76 (7.6)	54 (05.4)		
Income (\$)				
≤40	110 (11.0)	180 (18.0)	39.69	<0.001
41-80	142 (14.2)	246 (24.6)		
81-120	170 (17.0)	88 (08.8)		
121-160	34 (3.4)	14 (01.4)		
161-200	12 (1.2)	04 (0.4)		

In **Table 3**, there is a significant association between alcohol use and knowledge of stroke, however, other factors such as body mass index and lifestyle are not associated with knowledge of stroke.

Table 3: Association between sociodemographic factors and knowledge of stroke

Variable	Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory	Chi-square	P value
Source of information				
Health worker	240 (24.0)	133 (26.6)	2.743	0.097
Other sources	198 (19.8)	148 (29.6)		
BMI (Kg/M²)				
Normal (18.5-24.9)	196 (19.6)	244 (24.4)	0.314	0.855
Overweight (25-29.9)	164 (16.4)	186 (18.6)		
Obese (≥ 30)	92 (9.2)	118 (11.8)		
Physical exercise				
None	294 (29.4)	286 (28.6)	4.733	0.094
<5 days/week	144 (14.4)	106 (10.6)		
>5 days/week	72 (07.2)	98 (09.8)		
Alcohol use				
None	112 (11.2)	168 (16.8)	15.419	0.001
1-2 drinks/week	194 (18.4)	236 (23.6)		
3-6 drinks/week	84 (08.4)	94 (09.4)		
>7 drinks/week	22 (02.2)	100 (10.0)		
Chronic diseases				
None	88 (08.8)	130 (13.0)	0.369	0.832
Hypertension	236 (23.6)	316 (31.6)		
Diabetes mellitus	102 (10.2)	128 (12.8)		
Family history of stroke				
Yes	58 (05.8)	90 (09.0)	1.029	0.310
No	388 (38.8)	464 (46.4)		
I Know someone with stroke				
Yes	74 (7.4)	176 (17.6)	3.149	0.076
No	246 (24.6)	504 (50.4)		
Cigarette smoking				
Never smoked	316 (31.6)	354 (35.4)	0.665	0.717
Smoked in the past	130 (13.0)	14 (14.0)		
Currently smoking	24 (02.4)	36 (03.6)		

Discussion

The burden of stroke is a growing public health challenge in urban and rural communities in developing countries for which awareness is generally poor. The importance of community awareness of risk factors, knowledge, and early recognition of warning symptoms is critical to prevention. The findings of the current study showed that awareness and knowledge of stroke risk factors are generally poor comparable to studies [44, 45]. There was also poor perception of the implications of the stroke on personal well-being [46, 47], although contrasting reports have been reported from developing countries [48, 49]. The prevalence of self-reported hypertension among respondents was found in more than half of respondents [22]. The lack of knowledge and awareness of stroke risk factors found in the current study is comparable to previous studies [50, 51]. Access to accurate public health information is fundamental in enabling the recognition of risk factors and lifestyle changes needed to reduce risk. While community health workers are primarily the major sources of health information in most rural communities [43], increasing access to mass media, and the Internet in some semi-urban residents is creating new opportunities for access to health information [52]. However, in many rural communities' residents typically rely on family/friends and sometimes personal experience with acquaintances who are victims to be aware of stroke [39]. A significant proportion of the respondents had little unawareness of stroke and its risk factors comparable to other studies [53], although contrasting results have been reported [54, 55].

The poor awareness of stroke and its risk factors is related to poor health literacy in rural communities where there is acute lack of public health information. In most situations, the first awareness of stroke is from cases witnessed in the community and much of the information obtained is of poor quality which leaves individuals

with confusion, doubts, and unable to engage in changing modifiable risk factors. The knowledge of symptoms and early warning signs was generally poor, although, most respondents correctly identified paralysis, speech difficulties, and loss of sensation as common symptoms of stroke [56, 57]. The poor perception of stroke as a disease that is non-transmissible or inherited and the inability to relate an unhealthy lifestyle to stroke risk is comparable to previous studies [58, 59]. This may be due to related to inaccurate information, poor education, lack of healthcare facilities, poor health literacy, and absence of public health information systems in rural communities. This lack of public information makes it difficult for rural residents to properly assess their stroke risk in light of their current lifestyle choices [60, 61]. While a significant proportion of respondents were aware that they have hypertension, they demonstrated little knowledge of its relationship to a higher risk of stroke from uncontrolled blood pressure. The influence of demographic factors on awareness and knowledge of stroke has produced conflicting results. A previous study reported the contrasting influence of demographic factors on knowledge and attitudes towards stroke as well as its risk factors [49]. While this study showed significant association between knowledge of stroke and educational status [35, 62, 63], gender [64, 65], marital status [66, 67], occupation [68, 69], income [70] and age [71], no association with family history [72, 73], hypertension [74, 75], body mass index [76, 77], physical activity [75, 78], diabetes mellitus [79, 80], smoking [81] and previous episode of stroke [82, 83] was found in this study. Several studies from Nigeria have, however, reported contrasting from that observed in this study [64, 82, 84], which may be attributed to differences in study settings, assessment tools, level of health literacy, and access to health information resources. The observation from this study demonstrates the urgent need to strengthen the public health information system in rural/semi-urban areas where the majority of the population resides in Nigeria. The social and economic impact of stroke on household income and community productivity is enormous, particularly in rural areas where the major economic activity is related to agriculture and smallholder businesses.

Conclusion: Awareness and knowledge of stroke and its risk factors were generally poor among respondents. This lack of knowledge is influenced by demographic factors and a lack of access to health information. There is, therefore, a need to improve awareness of stroke risk factors among residents of rural communities.

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